

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

Title: SOP for GC Thermo Trace 1310 - ISQ 7000: Daily maintenance and Checking of the system

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Author: Hana Seličová

Summary:

This SOP summarizes the updated daily maintenance and checking for optimal responses and clean analysis without carry overs and contamination caused by dirty / old solvents. Those steps listed in daily maintenance need to be done every day before the start of the measurement or sample preparation.

DAILY MAINTENANCE**Exchange of the Glass liner and septum:**

NOTE: Before each Sequence/measurement it is necessary to replace the Glass Liner and Septum to prevent contamination of the spectra.

NOTE: During installation of the new liner and removing of the old one always wear gloves. Even with gloves eliminate the contact with the ends of the liner to prevent contamination.

Removing of the old liner:

1. Cool down the PTV inlet to 30°C (could be done through "Chromeleon → Instrument → Front/Back inlet → Inlet temperature" or directly on the "display of GC → Instrument control → Front inlet → Inlet temperature")
2. Cool down the oven temperature also to 30°C (could be done through "Chromeleon → Instrument → Oven → Oven temperature" or directly on the "display of GC → Instrument control → Oven → Oven temperature")
3. Turn off the gas flow ("Chromeleon → Instrument → Front/Back inlet → Column flow → Off" or directly on the "display of GC → Instrument control → Front inlet → Column flow → Off")
4. Open the plastic cover of the inlet.
5. Prepare a piece of aluminum foil on the table.

6. Unscrew the Septum cap by hand.
7. Put the Septum cap on the aluminum foil.
8. Take the slotted stubby driver and unscrew the Liner cap.
9. Put the Liner cap on the aluminium foil.
10. Take tweezers and remove and bin the septum.
11. Take the tool for removing the liner (purple-red tool with hollow ending) and carefully slowly put it on the liner from the top side.
12. Slowly take out the liner and bin it.
13. Take tweezers and remove the silicone Liner seal that may have stayed inside the PTV.
14. Now you have an empty PTV inlet and you can install the new liner.

NOTE: If the liner breaks during removing or installation, see the “SOP for GC 1310 7000 MS – Advanced Troubleshooting” where is this issue addressed)

Installation of the new liner:

1. Carefully take the new PTV liner from the box with tweezers.
2. Ensure you have it the correct way around – the wool should be in the upper half of the liner.
3. Take Liner Seal and put it carefully on the liner without touching the liner endings.
4. Put the liner into the inlet carefully, you should hear a glass “click” once the liner reaches the end of the inlet.

NOTE: If you don’t hear anything, there is chance you have the Liner Seal too low, and the liner hasn’t reached the end of inlet. Readjust and try again.

NOTE: Glass liner is fragile glass consumable. Do not drop the liner from the height, since it may break into shards.

5. Put back the Liner cap and screw it tight with the slotted stubby driver.
6. Put on the new septum ideally without touching the injection part.
7. Screw back the Septum cap by hand and close the lid.

NOTE: At least once a week the front part of the column in the inlet needs to be cut away to keep it clean and to overcome contamination.

NOTE: If you don't need to reinstall / cut the analytical column, skip directly to the step 11 of the "Reinstallation of the analytical column to the PTV inlet" to reheat the PTV inlet.

Reinstallation of the analytical column to the PTV inlet.

1. Unscrew the Terminal fitting using $\frac{1}{4}$ " wrench.
2. Carefully pull out the column out of the liner. If it doesn't go out, use grooved tweezers to pull it little more intensively.
3. Remove the ferrule by cutting it off.
4. Keep the rubber septa on the column, just move it little further from the end of the column.
5. Put the PTV ferrule and on it the Split nut (Figure 2).
6. Use silicon wafer and cut first 3 cm of the column.

NOTE: How to properly cut column is nicely explained in [the video from RESTEK](#). (in printed version scan the QR code (Figure 1) →)

Figure 1 - Column cutting video from RESTEK

7. Cut the column clean and check with the magnifying glass.
8. Take the ruler on the silicon wafer and check if the distance of the bottom part side of the PTV ferrule is exactly 30 mm far from the end of the column.
9. Put the column gently into the Terminal fitting.
10. Screw the Split nut to the Terminal fitting using $\frac{1}{4}$ " wrench.

NOTE: Screwing of the split nut requires to “have a feel for it” – this part is very easy to overtighten. Go slightly “below” the complete tightening.

Figure 2 - PTV inlet anatomy

11. Turn back on the gas flow (“Chromeleon → Instrument → Front/Back inlet → Column flow → On” or directly on the “display of GC → Instrument control → Front inlet → Column flow → On”)
12. Let the instrument purge the inlet with gas for a few minutes.
13. Heat the PTV inlet to the highest temperature used in the method to bake it out (could be done through “Chromeleon → Instrument → Front/Back inlet → Inlet temperature” or directly on the “display of GC → Instrument control → Front inlet → Inlet temperature”)
14. Heat the oven to the original temperature before maintenance (could be done through “Chromeleon → Instrument → Oven → Oven temperature” or directly on the “display of GC → Instrument control → Oven → Oven temperature”)

15. Check the leak of the system via the ISQ 7000 Dashboard (for more instructions see the part “Daily Checking of the system” in this SOP, for checking of the leak see [“SOP for GC ISQ 7000 Single Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer - Turning on, calibration, tuning, and shutting down the system”](#))

Changing of the solvents on solvent wash

NOTE: Before each Sequence/measurement replace Standard wash station solvents for needle wash for fresh ones and pour the waste vial

NOTE: Label your containers with specific solvent name and use that container specifically for that solvent only during that analysis. It is easier to keep track of what may be the contamination then.

1. Take the vials with solvents from the solvent wash station.
2. Place them in the fume hood on the aluminium foil.
3. Remove the lids and bin the aluminium foil septa from the last time.
4. Pour out the old solvents to the waste.
5. Take glass Pasteur pipette and first rinse the glass containers with small amount of the solvent that belongs to the specific container.
6. Pour out this solvent to the waste by circular movement of the container to rinse it properly.
7. Fill up the container with solvent.
8. Put on the piece of aluminium foil and cover with the plastic lid.

NOTE: Use aluminum foil instead of the rubber septa to overstep possible contamination from siloxanes, change this foil also every day when exchanging the solvents.

9. Repeat for each of the solvents.
10. Pour out the waste container.
11. Put the glass containers filled with new solvents back on the instrument and cover them with the metal lid.

Cleaning of the Hamilton syringes

NOTE: Before each Sequence/measurement clean the Hamilton syringes in the ultrasound bath – solvent used for cleaning is chosen based on the use of specific syringe.

1. Take the tools with syringes out of the TriPlus RSH.
2. Remove the syringe from the tool by unscrewing the upper ring holding the syringe tight in the tool and gently pull out the syringe.
3. Take a small Duran bottle or any other suitable glassware and put in the syringe for cleaning, aiming needle down.

NOTE: Take bottle big enough so the syringe does not overweight it and won't fall into the ultrasound bath and also small enough, so it allows you manipulation with the syringe's plunger.

4. Pour the solvent of choice to the bottle so it covers at least the level of the needle or slightly higher

NOTE: For syringe that is used to aspire stronger acid, water will be used for ultrasound cleaning. For syringe that is used to aspire polar organic solvent, miscible organic solvent will be used for ultrasound cleaning.

5. Turn on the ultrasound bath for few minutes and gently pull up and back down the plunger several times (repeat for duration at least 2 minutes, 5 minutes are better) to allow the solvent to go up in the plunger, not only into the needle.
 - a. Repeat for every syringe several times until there is no friction in the plunger.
 - b. Let the syringes in the solvent in the turned-on ultrasound bath for 30 minutes.
 - c. Take out the syringes out of the solvent, let them air-dry on the aluminum foil.
 - d. Assemble the Hamilton tool back together by putting the needle back in the tool and screwing the cap tight.

NOTE: When assembling the Hamilton tool back together, check which way is the colorful part of syringe facing and make sure the scale is easily visible from the point of view you are looking at the instrument when it is measuring. It will simplify checking of the proper injection and checking of potentially clogged syringe.

DAILY CHECKING OF THE SYSTEM

1. Check the Air & Water/Tune as shown in "[SOP for GC ISQ 7000 MS - Turning on, calibration, tuning, and shutting down the system](#)"
2. Check the Frequency Tune: ISQ Dashboard → Air & Water/Tune → Frequency Tune (Figure 3)

NOTE: The shape of the graphs in the Frequency Tune should look exactly as the one on the Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Checking frequency tune of the quadrupole

NOTE: Tuning of the machine shown in the "[SOP for GC ISQ 7000 MS - Turning on, calibration, tuning, and shutting down the system](#)" is **NOT** needed every day. Do it only when the source is clean, so the machine tunes on the clean parameters. Only thing that is needed daily is the **Check of the leak, filament and detector**. How to set up this tuning

file is shown in “SOP for GC ISQ 7000 MS – Advanced custom tuning and calibration instructions”.

NOTE: The default EI Check will not work since it does not have enabled check of the filament and the detector.

3. ISQ 7000 Dashboard → AutoTune → EI Check updated (custom version that covers also the checking of the filament and detector, for the setting of the custom Tune file see “SOP for GC ISQ 7000 MS – Advanced custom tuning and calibration instructions”)
4. ISQ 7000 Dashboard → View Tune Report (Figure 4)

NOTE: The Tune Report will differ based on the parameters that were set in the Custom Tune.

5. Check the (also other pages):
 - a. Leak (in %, should be below 10 %, differs column to column and will increase with amount of the column connections)
 - b. Detector gain and Multiplier voltage (below 2100 V) for state of Detector
 - c. Repeller voltage for state of Ion Source (3 = clean)

ISQ Tune Results

Lab: Recetox
 Tune Completed: Tue Oct 15 10:24:36 2024
 Tune File: AutoTune_EI_2024-10-15-10-24-36.isqtune
 Tune Type: EI Check updated
 Starting Tune File: (Last Saved Tune)

Instrument Name: ISQ
 Instrument ID: 2104078
 User: ISQ7000

Ion Source Type: EI
 Polarity: Positive
 Electron Lens Voltage: 5 V
 Electron Energy: 70 eV
 Emission Current: 50 µA
 Ion Guide Frequency: 1683.5
 Q1 Frequency: 1086.4
 Multiplier Voltage: 1200.0 V
 Detector Gain: 3.0 × 10⁵
 MS Transfer Line: 250.0 °C
 Filament Selection: 1
 Ion Source Temperature: 250.0 °C
 Fordline Pressure: 60 mTorr

Mass	Theory	Abundance	Relative Abundance	Isotope Mass	Theoretical Isotope Mass	Isotope Abundance	Isotope Ratio
69.01	69.00	27,073,898	100.00	70.07	70.00	381,809	1.41
218.96	218.99	25,235,968	93.21	220.01	219.99	984,231	3.90
263.96	263.99	6,673,449	24.65	265.02	264.99	346,352	5.19
312.12	311.99	0	0.00	313.12	312.99	0	NaN
502.01	501.97	1,828,091	6.75	503.07	502.97	179,452	9.82

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Figure 4 - Example of the tune file

6. Once everything above is checked, the instrument is **ready to measure**

QUICK CHECK OF DAILY MAINTENANCE:

- Exchanged liner and septum
- Exchanged solvents
- Sonicated syringes and checked that they are not clogged
- EI Check – everything passed, other parameters also look OK